

Deliverable D6.3 | D22

CSI-COP

Citizen Scientists Investigating Cookies and App GDPR compliance

CSI-COP Main Dissemination and Exploitation Event

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PU	Public	X
R	Report, DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs, DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc., OTHER: Other (Database, online tools, questionnaires, etc)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CI	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC.	

Version control

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Project partners: <https://csi-cop.eu/our-team/>

Privacy Champions

Citizen scientists

Stakeholders: in-person and online attendees

Building management in Avenue de Tervuren, 168, 1150 Brussels

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Executive Summary

CSI-COP main dissemination and exploitation event presented the diverse group of male and female privacy champions, aged 18-over 65 to variety of stakeholders. The event also provided an opportunity to demonstrate the second iteration of the searchable, web-based repository of trackers in websites and apps innovated from the investigations by the project's citizen scientists. Held across the week 23-26 May, CSI-COP consortium hosted sessions offering ten languages to online and in-person attendees learning about GDPR compliance in website cookie notices and app permissions. This deliverable report presents pictures from the vibrant event showcasing the importance of online personal data protection to members of the public from all walks of life.

Introduction

This public report presents an overview of CSI-COP project's main dissemination and exploitation event for task T6.3| D22 held in Brussels 23-26 May 2023. Designed as an intimate 'living museum', the project's privacy champions, emerging from CSI-COP's community of citizen scientists, presented their findings from web and app investigations to a variety of stakeholders attending in-person and online. A vibrant atmosphere across the week produced many fascinating discussions around personal data protection, children's right to privacy online, and the role of web and app developers in complying with the general data protection regulation (GDPR).

CSI-COP's test repository of cookies and trackers, innovated from the citizen scientists' web and app investigations, was demonstrated during the partners' sessions. Feedback offered on the repository aided in improving its development ready for launch on CSI-COP website by the end of May 2023.

Photographs taken across the four-days are included showing the diversity of participants, the breadth of activities, and the inclusive information-sharing in CSI-COP's dissemination and exploitation event successfully produced by T6.3 task leader and coordinating partner, Coventry University. Further photographs from the event will be uploaded to the news and events page on CSI-COP website. A special edition of CSI-COP newsletter will feature more of CSI-COP partners activities across the main project dissemination and exploitation event.

The following sections explain the set-up activity, the design of the partner sessions, the engagement activities, and CSI-COP aims beyond the life of the project concluding in August 2023.

Set-up for main event

The strategy for CSI-COP's communication, dissemination and exploitation activities were described in the project's public deliverable report D6.7| D32 (Shah et al., 2021). Citizen science engagement and stakeholder interaction were key to raise awareness of the project's objectives and disseminate CSI-COP's outcomes.

CSI-COP coordinating partner, Coventry University maintains a Europe hub in Brussels near Montgomery Metro. Two visits by the Coventry University team in February and March 2023 led to it being selected as an appropriate venue for CSI-COP project's main event. Coventry University's hub (office 022) is in an office building complex on Avenue de Tervuren, 168, 1150 Brussels with many organisations housed in the complex (see Image 1). This venue provided a good opportunity for drop-in by personnel in other offices. On set-up day, Monday 22 May 2023, Coventry University UK and the Brussels team displayed banners, notices, posters, leaflets ready for the Partner sessions beginning on Tuesday 23 May 2023 (Tables 1 & 2).

Image 1: (Left) Offices in Avenue de Tervuren, 168, 1150 Brussels

Table 1: (Below) CSI-COP inside Avenue de Tervuren, 168, 1150 Brussels

Coventry University set-up the venue as a small 'living museum' with posters created from CSI-COP newsletter interviews, bunting created from CSI-COP leaflets (see Table 2). For visitors to see, we also displayed CSI-COP's trophy from winning the '[Best Innovative Privacy Project](#)' in the inaugural [Picasso Privacy Awards](#) (Image 2).

Table 2: CSI-COP display in Coventry University (Europe) Hub in Brussels

<p>Poster of Advisory Board member, Professor Vian Bakir newsletter interview.</p>	<p>Consumables: CSI-COP bag for attendees with pen and notebook.</p>	<p>CSI-COP leaflets and consumables.</p>	<p>Poster of CSI-COP's Dr. Huma Shah article 'The Cookie Jar' in the International Teacher Magazine.</p>

Image 2: CSI-COP award for 'Best Innovative Privacy Project'

Main event design

The design of CSI-COP's main event enabled each partner to host either a hybrid, in-person only, or online only, session of two hours. The partners could offer their own language, or offer more than one language by splitting the two-hour session to present their contribution to their specific stakeholder audience. The week of 22-26 May 2023 was chosen, because in that week the major ['Computers, Privacy and Data Protection'](#) (CPDP2023) conference took place in Brussels: 24-26 May 2023. The schedule of partner sessions is shown in Table 3 overleaf. The first day, Tuesday 23 May was shared between Bar Ilan and Coventry Universities offering interactions in Hebrew and English. On the second day, University of Patras offered a Greek language session in the morning of Wednesday 24 May. In the afternoon of 24 May 2023, partner NaTE offered an online session in Hungarian and in English. (see Table 3). On the third day, the morning session offered Spanish interactions by partner Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona. In the afternoon of Thursday 25 May, Immer Besser offered interactions in Romanian and in English. The final day saw Czech Technical University offer Czech, Turkish and English interactions in the morning of Friday 26 May, while in the afternoon, University of UOULU

offered Finnish and Italian interactions. In all in-person and online attendees could interact with CSI-COP team members and citizen scientists in ten languages (see Table 3).

Table 3: CSI-COP Partner sessions in main event: 23-26 May 2023

Date of session	Day	Time: Central European Time (CET)	Language of session	Partner involved
23.05.2023	Tuesday	MORNING: 10am-12pm	Hebrew and English	BAR ILAN UNIVERSITY
23.05.2023		AFTERNOON: 2pm-4pm	English	COVENTRY UNIVERSITY
24.05.2023	Wednesday	MORNING: 10am-12pm	Greek	PANEPISTIMIO PATRON (University of Patras)
24.05.2023		AFTERNOON: 2pm-4pm	Hungarian and English	NOK A TUDOMANYBAN EGYESULET (NaTE)
25.05.2023	Thursday	MORNING: 10am-12pm	Spanish	UNIVERSITAT AUTONOMA DE BARCELONA (UAB)
25.05.2023		AFTERNOON: 2pm-4pm	English and Romanian	IMMER BESSER (IB)
26.05.2023	Friday	MORNING: 10am-12pm	Czech, Turkish and English	CESKE VYSOKE UCENI TECHNICKE V PRAZE (CTU)
26.05.2023		AFTERNOON: 2pm-4pm	Finnish and Italian	OULUN YLIOPISTO (UOULU)

Engagement and Activities

CSI-COP leveraged its achievements by presenting the privacy champions (PCs) who emerged from the project's community of citizen scientists in the main event. Privacy champions were present in-person in Brussels, others attended in online sessions. The PCs ranged in age from 18 to over 65. Male and female privacy champions participated enthusiastically. The list below shows:

- Bar Ilan University: in person attendance by 2PCs– both female.
- Coventry University: in person attendance by 4PCs- two females; two males.
- UPAT: in person attendance by 2PCs - one female; one male.
- NaTE: online attendance by 2PCs - one female; one male.
- IB: in person attendance by 2PCs- both female
- CTU online attendance by 4 PCs - two females; two males.

The offering of interactions with CSI-COP team members and citizen scientists in ten languages, along with the wide age-range, and the PCs male| female ratio of 6|10 demonstrates CSI-COP partner effort in achieving an inclusive family of CSI-COP privacy champions.

Additionally, the event allowed a platform to showcase the second iteration of CSI-COP’s repository, the web-based open-access knowledge resource of digital trackers (see D5.2|D19). Partners feedback on the first iteration (before the main event) allowed Coventry University’s sub-contractor for the repository innovation (Mr. Venkat Nanneboina of Xcel Resources Ltd.) to evolve the information retrieval, and present the website and app investigations with visualisations on the front page. The second iteration made the repository easier use for data extraction (Table 4). The repository launch on CSI-COP project website is beyond prototype (Technology Readiness Level 5- TRL5). With further feedback on the repository gained from attendees and citizen scientists during the main event the final version will see an improvement in the intelligent retrieval of CSI-COP’s website and app investigations. Continuous improvement in the web-based, open-access repository to the end of the project in August 2023 will render this free tool usable for a variety of stakeholders beyond the life of the project and be useful for up to two years afterwards (more in D5.2|D19 deliverable).

Table 4: Demonstrating 2nd iteration of CSI-COP repository in the main event

<p>Coventry University sub-contractor, Venkat Nanneboina of Xcel Resources Ltd., demonstrating the 2nd iteration of his Repository design</p>	<p>University of Patras Privacy Champion demonstrating the retrieval of Greek language website and app investigations from the 2nd iteration of the Repository.</p>	<p>Coventry University’s Dr. Huma Shah showing partners from CTU and online attendees how the 2nd iteration of the repository evolved from Partner feedback on 1st iteration.</p>

Dissemination and Exploitation impact

To disseminate CSI-COP project activities and exploit its results, including the two open-access databases created from citizen scientists investigations ([websites](#); [apps](#)), the [taxonomy of digital cookies and online trackers](#), partners focussed on inviting specific stakeholders they identified from the proposal phase and grant agreement. This included privacy and data protection professionals, policy makers, journalists, stakeholders in informal and formal science education. CSI-COP’s Brussels event promoted the project’s GDPR-awareness and innovative activities by disseminating CSI-COP citizen scientists and team members’ website cookies and app tracker findings through social media posts (LinkedIn; Twitter), through various partner networks, word-of-mouth, and a [press release](#) from [Coventry University](#).

CSI-COP partners reached widely to secure attendance from a variety of interested individuals. This included very senior people invited by partners, including Bar Ilan University (BIU) and University of Patras (UPAT) to participate in the CSI-COP’s main event. Attendees in person or online included:

- Online attendance included individuals from as far apart as Mexico City (CU 23/5 Tuesday PM), Miami (CU-UOULU 26/5 Friday PM), and Lecce-Italy (23 & 26/5 PM).

- **Amit Ashkenazi**, a CPDP2023 conference registrant and CPDP2023 panel member, was secured by BIU to attend BIU's session in-person (23/5 Tuesday AM). Amit Ashkenazi is the Legal Advisor of The Israel National Cyber Directorate which includes both the National Cyber Bureau and the National Cyber Security Authority in the Prime Minister's Office. Amit is in charge of developing and deploying the Directorate's domestic and international legal policy, and legal counsel for both INCB's activities (policy international, internal), and the National Cyber Security Authority (policy, regulation, operation). He also teaches at Haifa University, Israel. https://csrcl.huji.ac.il/sites/default/files/csrl/files/amit_ashkenazi_0.pdf
- **Avital Grinberg**, the President of European Union of Jewish Students. <https://www.linkedin.com/in/avital-grinberg-773b31113/>. Avital explained in BIU's session about the case they submitted to the court in Germany against Twitter disseminating antisemitic content.
- **Michal Graf**, the Bilateral Relations Officer Mission of Israel to the EU, is an Israeli Embassy representative who attended BIU's session in person.
- <https://www.linkedin.com/in/michal-graf-81800b98/>
- **Moran Nagar** attended in person BIU's session in person. Moran is a tech company representative from Bank ONE ZERO -the new first digital online bank in Israel founded in 2019 by the founder of Mobileye (autonomous cars).
- **Tzanetos Karantzis**, the Ambassador for Greece in Brussels, attended UPAT's Greek session in person in the morning of Wednesday 25 May.
- **Anna Michelle Asimakopoulou**, Greek MEP in Brussels also attended UPAT's Greek language session on 25 May.
- **Joan Raventós**, journalist from Catalan TV attended in-person in the morning of Thursday 25 May interviewing UAB's Dr. Eva Jove, exploring CSI-COP repository, and learning about trackers in his website.
- **Erika Gutmane** and **Tom Scott Redford** members of CEPIS (<https://cepis.org/>) attended CTU's session in person (26/5 AM).
- **Lenka Procházková**, Head of the Czech Liaison Office for Education and Research in Brussels (CZELO), also attended CTU's session in-person
- **Nathalie Marchand** of EBN (<https://ebn.eu/>) located in the same CU Hub Brussels complex attended in-person to meet with CU (26/5 Friday AM), also talked with UOULU's Dr. Ulrico Celentano.
- **Gabriella Leo** EU policy maker attended online in CU's session (23/5 Tuesday AM).
- Tech-related people attended online in CU's session (23/5 Tuesday AM).
- CU staff and PhD students attended online in CU session (23/5 Tuesday PM)

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Other attendees online and in-person included digital tech professionals, academics, PhD students, professors and teenage students from the Lycee Hellenique in Brussels. CSI-COP Advisory Board member Julius Stuller also attended CTU's morning session on Friday 26 May. BIU's Dr Maayan Zhitomirsky-Geffet met with **Jonathan Rosenzweig**, the Deputy Head of Mission, at the Mission of Israel to the European Union & NATO. <https://www.linkedin.com/in/jonathan-rosenzweig/>. Mr Rosenzweig did not attend CSI-COP event in person, but sent his representative and met Dr. Zhitomirsky-Geffet immediately after. In this personal meeting, Dr. Zhitomirsky-Geffet described the project and its results to Mr Rosenzweig in detail. Mr Rosenzweig published a post about his meeting

with Dr. Zhitomirsky-Geffet and CSI-COP project on his LinkedIn profile: <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7066828302765674497/>.

CSI-COP Legacy

All sessions in CSI-COP's main event hosted animated discussions around GDPR compliance in cookie banners and privacy policies on websites, and app permissions. The partners' invited privacy champions explained to stakeholders why they joined CSI-COP project as citizen scientists and what they learnt about how to better protect their personal data online. Attendees in the sessions read information on the posters, in the leaflets, and played games, including a free online cookie avoidance game. Friday 26 May attendees gained an opportunity to play a bespoke privacy game designed by CTU partner to engage citizen scientists in the Czech Republic during the difficult period emerging from COVID-19 lockdowns in late 2021 and into 2022. CSI-COP's main event has left a lasting impression on the privacy champions and stakeholders attending on how collaboration between researchers and the general public can produce innovative results. The CSI-COP '[Taxonomy of digital cookies and online trackers](#)' (Shah et al., 2023), and the searchable repository of trackers could not have been achieved without the invaluable time offered on a volunteer basis by CSI-COP's citizen scientists. A citizen science forum is being set-up from interested parties collaborating in the project to carry CSI-COP results forward. CSI-COP's final policy recommendation will include suggestions for standardisation in cookie notices and banners, and privacy policies. Some photographs from CSI-COP'S main event feature next.

References:

Shah, H., Gialelis, Y., Konstantinopoulos, I., Lantavou, K., Karakonstanti, A., Rigler, D., Stepankova, O., Ignat, A. and Celentano, U. (2023). *Taxonomy of Cookies and Digital Trackers* (deliverable D5.1|D18). CSI-COP EU Horizon2020 SwafS 15-2019 funded project (GA 873169). Available from CSI-COP project results page here: <https://csi-cop.eu/project-results/taxonomy-of-cookies-and-online-trackers/>

Shah, H., Goodman, D., Stepankova, O., Rigler, D., Hinsenkamp, M., Pocs, M., Celentano, U., Vallverdú, J., Zhitomirsky-Geffett, M., Ignat, T., Gialelis, Y. and Forbes, N. (2021). *CSI-COP Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (CDE) Plan* (deliverable D6.7|D32). CSI-COP EU Horizon2020 SwafS 15-2019 funded project (GA 873169). Available from EU CSI-COP Cordis results page here: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/873169/results>

Other CSI-COP project results (public reports) can be read online, or downloaded from here:

<https://csi-cop.eu/projectresults/>

